

**Effect Computerization The tax system on internal control evaluation
(A field study on the Federal Tax Office – Sudan)**

Impact of The Computerization of Tax System on
Internal Control Evaluation
(field study on the federal tax office-Sudan)

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Abstract

The study examined the impact of computerization of the tax system on internal control evaluation. The problem of the study was to transform the tax system from traditional to electronic, which is one of the mechanisms that can reduce the risk of corruption, especially that which results from the complexity of procedures, wasting the taxpayer's time, and the use of mediation and favoritism in meeting the needs of taxpayers, in light of the large and rapid developments in technology that resulted in this. Increasing attention and focus on customer service. The system's management always resorts to evaluating internal control to identify the risks it faces in order to avoid them. The study aimed to identify tax computerization and explain its impact on the tax system, identify the internal control system and explain its impact on electronic systems and procedures for protecting electronic systems. And to identify tax governance and the possibility of activating it in the Sudanese tax system. To achieve the objectives of the study, the following hypotheses were tested: There is a statistically significant relationship between the computerization of the tax system and the evaluation of internal control. The study relied on a number of approaches through which facts related to the objectives of the study are collected. It relied on the deductive approach, and inductive, Using the historical and analytical descriptive approach, the study reached a number of results, the most important of which are: The Bureau has an information base on tax payers. However, this available information is not updated on a continuous basis, and thus the taxpayers information becomes outdated. The computerized system helps in speeding up the completion of work if modern communication networks and good infrastructure are available, and the Internal Audit Department of the Bureau submits a report. On internal control, it explains the strengths and weaknesses, and that computerization of the tax system helps in activating tax governance by creating interaction platforms between the parties to the system. The study came out with a number of recommendations, the most important of which are: necessity Updating the tax payers information base on a regular basis, increasing the state's interest and providing the required financial support for the computerization project, expanding the use of electronic invoices and prohibiting work without identification numbers, paying attention to the internal control report and working to address deviations, working to activate governance over the tax system, paying attention to the office's website and developing it. And get it back to work.

Keywords: tax system, internal control

المستخلص

تناولت الدراسة أثر حوسبة النظام الضريبي على تقويم الرقابة الداخلية، تمثلت مشكلة الدراسة في تحويل النظام الضريبي من تقليدي إلى إلكتروني يعد أحد الأليات التي يمكن أن تحد من خطورة الفساد خاصة الذي ينتج من تعقيد الإجراءات وإهدار زمن الممول وأستخدام الوساطة والمحسوبية في قضاء حوائج الممولين، في ظل التطورات الكبيرة و المتسارعة في التكنولوجيا التي نتج عنها زيادة الاهتمام والتركيز على خدمة العملاء دائما ما تلجأ إدارة النظام إلى تقويم الرقابة الداخلية للتعرف على المخاطر التي تواجهها لتعمل على تجنبها، هدفت الدراسة إلى التعرف على الحوسبة الضريبية وبيان أثرها على النظام الضريبي والوقوف على نظام الرقابة الداخلية وبيان أثره على الانظمة الالكترونية وإجراءات حماية النظم الالكترونية ، والتعرف على الحوكمة الضريبية ومدى امكانية تفعيلها على النظام الضريبي السوداني ، لتحقيق أهداف الدراسة تم إختبار الفرضيات التالية : هناك علاقة ذات دلالة احصائية بين حوسبة النظام الضريبي وتقويم الرقابة الداخلية ، إعتمدت الدراسة على عدد من المناهج التي يتم من خلالها جمع الحقائق التي تتعلق باهداف الدراسة حيث إعتمدت على المنهج الاستنباطي ، والاستقرائي ، والتاريخي والمنهج الوصفي التحليلي ، توصلت الدراسة لعدد من النتائج أهمها : تتوفر لدى الديوان قاعدة معلومات عن دافعي الضريبة ولكن هذه المعلومات المتوفرة لا يتم تحديثها بصورة مستمرة وبذلك تصبح معلومات دافعي الضريبة قديمة ، وأن النظام المحوسب يساعد في سرعة انجاز الاعمال إذا توفرت شبكات اتصال حديثة وبنية تحتية جيدة ، وأن قسم المراجعة الداخلية بالديوان يقوم برفع تقرير عن الرقابة الداخلية يوضح به نقاط القوة والضعف ، وان حوسبة النظام الضريبي تساعد في تفعيل الحوكمة الضريبية من خلال خلق منصات تفاعل بين أطراف النظام ، خرجت الدراسة بعدد من التوصيات أهمها : ضرورة تحديث قاعدة معلومات دافعي الضريبة بصورة دورية ، وزيادة إهتمام الدولة وتوفير الدعم المادى المطلوب لمشروع الحوسبه ، والتوسع في استخدام الفاتورة الالكترونية وحظر العمل بدون أرقام تعريفية ، والإهتمام بتقرير الرقابة الداخلية والعمل على معالجة الانحرافات ، العمل بتفعيل الحوكمة على النظام الضريبي ، الاهتمام بموقع الديوان وتطويره واعادته للعمل.

الكلمات المفتاحية: النظام الضريبي ، الرقابة الداخلية .

:the introduction

Taxes are an important and essential resource General revenues of the state, As a means of redistributing national ,income, financing development projects Its performance is effective in directing and implementing the state's overall financial and economic policies. The tax system in Sudan has developed over the past years and expanded geographically and now includes a network of departments and offices to cover all parts of Sudan. Within the framework of the state's approach to electronic government in order to develop and control public service, it has begun The Bureau is implementing the computerization of all tax procedures and transactions with the aim of developing the Bureau's performance by building a secure and strong information base to facilitate the circulation of information, which will be reflected in increasing revenues – reducing the cost of collection, combating the informal economy, and facilitating electronic services for .taxpayers in a way that achieves high levels of trust, satisfaction and justice

The internal control system is of great importance, as it identifies deviations and risks and works to address or reduce .them and protect public units from embezzlement, loss and misuse

: the study Problem

The transformation of procedures from traditional to electronic is one of the mechanisms that can reduce the risk of corruption, especially that which results from the complexity of procedures, the waste of the financier's time, and the use of mediation and favoritism in meeting the needs of financiers. The internal control system is considered the first line of defense for institutions, and for the administration to ensure the effectiveness of this system and the extent of reliance on it. It resorts to evaluating it periodically to identify the weak points and risks facing the system. **The research problem**

:can be formulated in the following questions

1– ?Does computerization of the tax system help in evaluating the internal control of the Tax Office

2– Is there a statistically significant relationship between the computerization of the tax system and the evaluation of ?internal control

:Purpose of the study

:The study seeks to achieve the following objectives

.Study the impact of computerization of the tax system on evaluating internal control in the Bureau –1

.Statement of the relationship Between computerization of the tax system and internal control evaluation –2

:the importance of studying

:The importance of the study is as follows

:Scientific importance

. The scarcity of writings on this topic due to the modernity of tax computing, the importance of internal control in institutions .and its role in identifying deviations and addressing them

. :Practical importance

Evaluating the internal control system in the Bureau is considered of some importance given the role of the Bureau in financing the state treasury. Tax computing represents an introduction to developing and moving the Bureau to the verge of advanced systems

:Study hypotheses

:To achieve the objectives of the study, the following hypotheses were tested

1- ?Does computerization of the tax system help in evaluating the internal control of the Tax Office

2- Is there a statistically significant relationship between the computerization of the tax system and the evaluation of ?internal control

:Study methodology

.Descriptive analytical method

:The theoretical framework for responsibility accounting and previous studies**:First: Definition of tax**

Simon and Christopher defined it in their book (The Economics of Taxation) as a compulsory obligation by the public authorities without receiving anything in return (Khaled, 1970), and Al-Huimel defined it as (a compulsory, non-punitive financial deduction determined by the state, and natural and legal persons are obligated to pay it to the state permanently, and without compensation, so that it can The state is able to carry out its economic, social and political functions (Saeed .(2013

:Second: Tax characteristics

:The tax is characterized by a set of characteristics, which are

Tax -1 duty Cash: any that it You pay in appearance monetary , And that Response For requirements Economic system And they looked forward To achieve principle Justice Tax.

You pay -2 Tax Jabra: And this Means that Assigned With tax not for him Option in Push it To the state but rather, he forced on that.

Tax -3 You pay As Final: If Assigned Pay Tax In a way ultimate , But this no Returns prohibited some Of which in condition presentation Stab or Darken.

Tax -4 You pay from Without Opposite Direct: In Assigned Motivation For tax no Enjoy In return direct ?Why did he pay it , But it is It benefits from Services the public that Its progress Country **(Mohammed, 2015)**.

:Third: Tax rules

In order for the tax to achieve its goals and functions, the tax must be imposed according to the rules

:Observe these most important rules

The rule of justice: Justice emerges from the principle of equality before the tax, whereby the tax applies to all funds -1 in all their forms and manifestations and to all persons, and there are no privileged classes that are not subject to the .tax

,**The rule of certainty:** Certainty or certainty is one of the most important factors for tax stability and therefore social -2 economic and political stability. This is done by formulating tax legislation so that it is clear and away from ambiguity and .what is likely to be interpreted by issuing executive regulations, books and publications

The rule of appropriateness: The tax must be collected at the times and in the most appropriate ways for the -3 .taxpayer

The rule of economy: Economy in tax expenditures so that the taxpayer cannot bear a sacrifice that is not beneficial -4 .or inappropriate, or a comparison between the collection and the cost of collecting this tax

.**An annual tax rule:** to be taken on an annual basis, provided that taxpayers are held accountable (year by year) -5

The rule of flexibility: reconciliation between the interest of each taxpayer, for whom the tax represents a social -6 .duty, and the interest of the state that has the right to sovereignty

Researchers believe that these rules are of great importance that the tax administration and the legislative body must take into account when imposing any new tax or estimating and collecting an imposed tax, because by applying them .correctly, voluntary compliance increases and the cost decreases Collection. (Hassan, 2015 AD)

:Fourth: Types of taxes in the Sudanese system

1- Income tax (business profits): Income tax (business and individual profits) is considered one of the old taxes and is one of the most important direct taxes. The revenues generated from it represent the largest portion and play an essential role in the state budget. They also have a great influence on economic activities and are one of the .important means of redistributing national income and encouraging investment

2- Personal income tax (salaries): It is an annual tax due, monthly collection, withheld at the source, originating from the pure labor component and imposed on a natural person. It is collected by the employer (government or private sector) and submitted to the tax office on a monthly basis, within a period not exceeding the fifteenth of the month. the next

1- Stamp duty: Stamp duty is one of the taxes imposed on the use of wealth or the completion of transactions related to it. It is a specific tax that does not take into account the personal circumstances of the taxpayer and does not apply to it the characteristics of a fee, as most legislation has traditionally called it. The stamp duty is an amount collected by the government from individuals on Documents and some various transactions as fees for the service provided to them. The fee must be a small amount compared to the service provided and is paid by the beneficiary of the service or the person requesting the service without creating a heavy burden on him. The stamp duty usually :achieves two goals

.A- Giving the document an official and legal form

.B- Supporting the public treasury

2- :National contribution for Sudanese working abroad

The income tax law did not apply to Sudanese abroad, and based on the recommendation of the international expatriate conference, in support of the public treasury and effective contribution to development projects, the first income tax law was issued on Sudanese working abroad in November 1981, enabling the tax to be imposed on their income, whether it came from employment, business profits, or real estate rent. Then the law was amended in the year 1982 AD so that the basis for imposing the tax was profession, not income. Workers abroad mean the Sudanese who work abroad for a period exceeding a total of one hundred and eighty–three days, other than those who work in .the diplomatic corps (Abdel Qader, 2014 AD)

3- :Agricultural taxes

.Agricultural activity, both plant and animal, is considered the main activity for the majority of the population of Sudan Agriculture contributes a high percentage to the national income, but the contribution of the agricultural sector to direct tax revenues is weak and almost negligible. Despite the agricultural activity falling under the umbrella of the business profits tax, what is subject to the business profits tax is corporate activity. Ltd. in the field of agriculture, in addition to rain–fed projects, and the tax was estimated on agricultural activity in the categories of the business profits tax. In agricultural taxes were canceled as a result of protests by farmers who considered taxes among the basic ,2001 obstacles to the development of agriculture. Currently, agriculture, both its plant and animal parts, is treated at a price of (zero), despite the abolition of agricultural taxes. There was no significant development in agriculture

4- Professional Taxes: Professionals are self–employed professionals and their income is subject to tax in accordance with the provisions of the Income Tax Law of 1986. They are estimated according to the basis of estimating business profits tax by determining the total income and then deducting the expenses necessary for the work to arrive at the net taxable income. These categories include: medical professions, lawyers, engineers in all their .specializations, and artists. Consultants (economics, law, taxes, etc.) and auditors

5- Value–added tax: The implementation of the value–added tax dates back to the year 1954 AD, when it was applied for the first time in France. Then its application spread in the European Union countries, some Asian and African

countries, and Latin American countries. As for Sudan, it was one of the recommendations of the Tax Reform Committee in the year 1994 AD, and a law was issued. Value-added tax in 1999. The tax was implemented in and value-added tax appeared in Sudan. The urgent need to increase revenues is to contain the high and ,2000 growing deficit in the state's general budget and increase revenues due to the decline in general sales tax revenues during recent years as a percentage of tax revenues, and as a percentage of taxes on goods and services.

:First: Definition of tax computing

Tax computerization is defined as the use of computers in various tax collection operations, facilitating and facilitating the process of taxpayers with tax departments, reducing the time required for the tax process among taxpayers, and focusing the attention of the tax inspector on field work, which lies at the heart of the tax examination process, instead of being preoccupied with office work resulting from routine. Which accompanies the receipt of collection and the conclusion of a deal between government departments and taxpayers to reduce methods of tax evasion for taxpayers and companies) Qassim 2018 (

,define tax computing as an electronic platform that facilitates the conduct of all tax transactions (inventory, assessment and collection operations) with great speed and accuracy in results, helps in voluntary compliance, and provides real .information that helps in proper planning

:Second: The reasons that led to the emergence of tax computerization

:High cost of collecting taxes –1

.The cost standard is used as one of the most important indicators to measure the effectiveness of the tax administration Therefore, it has become necessary to know how much the tax administration requires in terms of collection management expenses. The tax administration in both the United States of America and Sweden is considered one of the most ,effective administrations, as the collection cost is estimated at 0.5%, while in Spain In Canada, it is estimated at 1.05% while the percentage in France reached 1.6%. This is mainly due to the growth in tax awareness among taxpayers, as well as the availability of the material and human capabilities and means necessary to perform the work of these .departments

:The increase in the number of administrative structures and the deterioration of their status –2

Tax administrations in a number of countries around the world suffer from an increase in the number of administrative structures and the similarity of their tasks. This contradicts the desired goal of achieving an administration with less .Cost Ministère2004) (

:The expansion of the parallel economy and the spread of fraud and tax evasion –3

The parallel sector is defined as all economic sectors that do not have a legal existence. The chaotic openness of the ,market economy has resulted in the emergence of unethical practices on the part of some companies and merchants such as not declaring business numbers and realized profits and tampering with invoices for the purpose of fraud and tax evasion. Given the seriousness of this situation, which It has become a threat to national economies and the modest capabilities and means of the tax administration in counting parallel economy activities. It has become necessary to .computerize it to facilitate tax collection tasks and reduce tax evasion

:Third: Objectives of tax computing

:Various tax administrations seek to computerize their tax systems for the following goals(Ministry2007)

:Raising the financial return of the tax –1

With the implementation of the computerization program and good follow-up of taxpayer files, it is expected that the financial return rate will rise annually until it reaches acceptable rates compared to some countries of similar importance .in terms of economic activity, whose tax collection rates range between 25% and 30% of the domestic product

:Combating the phenomena of fraud and tax evasion –2

It is considered one of the most important goals of the tax computerization process, as the transition of the tax file management process from the multiple tax system to the management system by categories (large, medium, and small taxpayers), as well as the introduction of modern methods and techniques in organization would allow control over the management of taxpayer files. Most importantly, given that taxation energies are concentrated in a limited number of large institutions, this also allows for careful follow-up of taxable persons' declarations and their periodic review in a single tax file, filling gaps in the face of attempts at fraud and tax evasion, and thus improving the return of tax revenues

:Reducing administrative costs and increasing taxpayer satisfaction –3

By implementing the tax computerization program and introducing electronic management systems, the public tax administrations aim to bring about a radical and comprehensive change in the content of traditional administration and to achieve their general strategic objectives with high efficiency and at a lower cost through the use of the enormous and advanced capabilities of new information and communication technologies.

:First: Steps to computerize the tax system

:The tax administration computerization system is designed according to the following steps ((Al-Baz, 2015

:System infrastructure design –1

The bottom layer of the electronic cloud is designed and is referred to as devices as a service. It includes all services ,such as storage, backup copies, transferring tax files to an integrated electronic system, abandoning computer storage and converting to network storage while maintaining backup copies as well as databases. This is why the reference leads to: Infrastructure as a cloud service represents a complete virtual structure that dispenses with the need to own :connections and devices. Examples of companies that apply this are companies that provide the following servicesOP source Verizon ,HP ,Amazon:

2- :Designing the platform or computer environment

The next level of cloud is what is used by organizations that develop or modify their software applications. Platform as a service in the cloud is defined as a set of software and development tools for products that are hosted on the provider's infrastructure. Developers create applications on the provider's platform over the Internet. They are used as programming destinations and portals to the Tax Authority's website that are installed on the computer of the recipient of the service from among the taxpayers. E-government needs to invest in the infrastructure necessary to build the web and applications, but platforms can also be rented, and there are currently no standards for environmental operation or the ability to carry data in the cloud. Some providers allow software to be transferred to the consumer requesting the service from clients outside the service provider's platform. Therefore, it is emphasized that the design of the platform is a software directed to designers, developers and programmers through which it is possible to build databases to provide the needs of taxpayers and the Tax Authority of the concerned parties, through special websites of the Tax Authority or .electronic spaces hosted by hosting companies while preserving the needs of Necessary confidentiality of information

:Designing the software necessary to complete tax services –3

It is the highest level of the cloud, where software applications or data related to taxpayers' requests and the type of information available to provide the service are hosted, as well as the type of data requested by the tax file to achieve the fairness of the tax examination. This is the point of benefit and creating permanent feedback according to the .development of tax legislation and the multiplicity of financial control systems for taxpayers' computers among them Various government departments that have a role in enriching the tax file. It is possible to invest in supporting this software in light of the e-government appropriations in the items allocated for this from the state's general budget, and

the investment is achieved through these devices wherever they are located, and in this case it is possible for the user .to develop his programs at the lowest cost or rent these programs

:Second : Definition of internal control

Defined by the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants(AICPA) The American Institute of Certified Public Accountants Internal control was defined in 1949 AD as including the organizational plan, means of coordination, and standards used in the facility with the aim of protecting its assets, monitoring and controlling the accuracy of accounting data and the extent of reliance on it, with the aim of raising production efficiency and encouraging commitment to implementing established administrative policies. (Majid, 2006, p. 64.)

) The Committee of Sponsoring OrganizationsCOSO defines it as (processes influenced by the organization's board of (directors, management, and other individuals in the organization that are designed to provide reasonable assurance that the organization will achieve its goals). (Bakr, 2017, p. 158)

1- : Types of internal control

:Internal control is divided into four sections

A- Prevention control: Its aim is to prevent error or fraud from occurring before it occurs, such as procedures for .separating tasks and supervision

B- Discovery oversight: From its name it is clear that its goal is to discover errors after they occur, such as the settlement .process Which can detect specific errors in recording entries related to the estimate

.C- Correction control: This is the inspection and correction of the error discovered through discovery control

D- Direction control: This procedure is designed primarily to obtain positive results from inspection programs for this .purpose

The researcher believes that when these types of control are applied, deviations will be reduced to a minimum because they help prevent errors, errors that were not prevented will be discovered, errors that were not discovered will be corrected, and so on. (Nabil, 2016, p. 4)

2- The importance of internal control:

The internal control system is of great importance to the institution, and this importance is represented in a group of :elements, which are as follows

:A- Planning

Planning represents the first main element of administrative activity in the institution and includes defining the main objectives of the institution in general, and defining sub-objectives at the level of different departments and divisions that .contribute to achieving the main objectives of the institution

:B- Organization

Organization includes preparing and designing the organizational structure of the institution, defining the different responsibilities and authorities for each administrative level within the institution, in addition to organizing the various .works and activities in the institution

:C- Guidance

It aims to develop and specify the various instructions and regulations governing the work and communicate them to all employees in the institution, guiding the employees first-hand in order to achieve the main and subsidiary objectives of .the institution's business activities in a sound and effective manner

:D- Supervision

Its scope includes monitoring and supervising the performance of work and tasks with the aim of giving advice and setting .the necessary directions to prevent the recurrence of deviations or errors

:E- Monitoring and Evaluation

It includes monitoring the performance of employees and evaluating the performance of various administrative levels, in addition to

Examining work and tasks, evaluating results, and preparing a report on them. (Amer, 2018, p. 55)

:Fifth: Characteristics of internal control

:Internal control is characterized by a set of characteristics, which are as follows

A- Permanence: Internal control enables the organization to continue, as it adapts and keeps pace with development in the organization's environment

.B- Comprehensiveness: Internal control relates to all the organization's activities

.C – Independence: Internal control must respect the resources and methods used in the institution

.D- Harmony: Internal control must be established according to the characteristics of the institution and its environment

(Fayez, 2017, p. 10)

Researchers believe that an organization that applies an internal control system is able to identify deviations early and the risks are reduced, which helps in its continuity and development

: Previous studies**: Study by Amna Hassan 2006 AD**

The study examined the impact of the use of information technology on the internal control system. The study aimed to conduct an analysis of the technology systems used in internal control. The problem of the study was that traditional methods are not suitable for evaluating the efficiency and effectiveness of internal control systems based on information technology, as it reached the most important results, the most important of which is that the use of information technology in internal control systems helped in the efficiency, effectiveness and speed of evaluating these systems and helped in preserving the facility's property and the integrity of accounting data. And her health

Study by Ahmed Mohamed 2012 AD

The study dealt with the use of information and communication network technology in supporting the tax information system. The study aimed to define With importance System the information Tax And his role in practical Accountability Tax with Taxpayers and definition Understandably Technology network the information And communications And its types and clarification Advantages Resulting on Use Technology network the information and communications from before Tax departments, represented The problem of the study is that the income tax departments in the city of Erbil lack the basic requirements that can be considered a sound information system that can be relied upon to support the tax accounting process. The study used the descriptive approach and the deductive approach. The study reached results including that the tax departments in the research sample currently lack what An integrated and sound information system can be created. Information and communications network technology provides a wide scope for benefiting from the applications of this technology in supporting the tax accounting process. Tax departments' use of information and communications network technology will enhance confidence between both parties to the tax accounting process (tax departments and taxpayers)

Study now is strange, 2009 AD

.The study addressed the role of the internal control system in light of the electronic accounting information system. The study aimed to identify internal control and its methods to demonstrate the extent of its contribution to achieving banking safety under the electronic accounting information system. The problem of the study was represented by the failure of commercial banks to follow the scientific and practical foundations in the work of internal control followed. In which, despite the widespread introduction of electronic accounting information systems, the study sought to test the following hypothesis that internal control has a major role in light of accounting information systems, through its methods

in verifying that business is proceeding according to what is planned in all efficiency, effectiveness, and economy, and on time. The study used the method Using the descriptive, analytical and questionnaire approach for the field study, the study reached results including that there is an urgent need for effective internal control to keep pace with developments in the information technology environment and in a way that facilitates the possibility of its integration with administrative .and financial information systems

From the above, we see that this study addressed the role of the internal control system in light of the electronic .accounting information system, while the study addressed the impact of computerization on evaluating internal control

study Flossy Wawira & others ,2017

The study aimed to study the effects of the electronic tax system on the efficiency of tax collection in the local tax administration of the Kenya Revenue Authority(KRA) in the Rift Valley region. The problem of the study was that the Kenya Revenue Authority is one of the organizations that relies heavily on the electronic systems strategy in order to fulfill its basic responsibility. In collecting revenue on behalf of the Government of Kenya, according to the Kenya Revenue Authority website (2015), the KRA is ,a semi-autonomous government agency that aims to assess, collect administer and enforce laws relating to revenue and tax administration. The electronic tax system forms part of the revenue collection reforms by the Kenya Revenue Authority. whose primary motive is to enhance tax collections and tax efficiency and therefore, tax revenues are increasing rapidly due to the rapid economic development of the country that has accelerated in this regard and there are still challenges that are not beyond the indicators of revenue increase that the country enjoys and other economic and financial experts argue that the increase may not be Necessarily due to the introduction of the electronic system, but there are other factors. The electronic tax system includes modern technology, which is in the form of computers, the Internet, and software applications. This technology is considered effective only when it is handled by well-trained employees who are integrated into the organization's workflow. The study focuses on Uasin Gishu District as a study. case and will try to find out how online tax payment and filling has affected tax collections on local taxes in this area. The study found that employee efficiency is an important indicator of tax collection efficiency and respondents can access and operate the electronic tax system but taxpayers seeking clarifications on issues The online tax system was minimal and the handling of the e-tax system issues raised by taxpayers was not satisfactory and the KRA management was experiencing system downtime as they were not fully .equipped and understaffed in their control centre .

:Field study tool

.The researcher used the questionnaire form as the main means of collecting data from the study sample

: Statistical reliability and validity /1

To calculate the validity and statistical reliability of the questionnaire, a survey was taken, and the reliability and validity of the questionnaire were calculated from the survey sample according to the split-half equation. Table No. (1) shows : the results of the reliability and statistical validity of the answers of the survey sample members

Table No. (1)

Results of reliability and statistical validity of the sample members' answers

Self-honesty coefficient	Stability coefficient	Hypotheses
%91	%82	The first axis
%93	%86	The second axis
%97	%94	The questionnaire is complete

Source: Prepared by the researcher from field study data, 2023 AD

It is clear to the researcher from Table No. (1) that the percentage of the reliability coefficient and the self-validity coefficient using the Crenbach Alpha equation for the statements for the entire questionnaire are very high, which gives a good indicator of the strength and validity of the questionnaire and the understanding of its statements by the respondents, and then relying on them to test the study hypotheses

:Statistical methods used –2

) To achieve the objectives of the study and verify its hypotheses, the statistical program SPSS was used, which stands for Statistical Package for the Social Sciences. Excel was also used to the graphical forms required in the implementation. This is to use the results of the following statistical methods .study

1. .Frequencies and percentages of sample members' answers to the statements
 2. Graphs and percentages of the answers of individuals in the study sample
 3. .to calculate the reliability coefficient and statistical validity Cronbach Alpha
 4.) And the arithmetic mean .of the sample members' answers to the statements (
 5. T .test to test hypotheses–
- Pearson's simple linear correlation.6
- Simple linear regression .7

:Data analysis and hypothesis testing

:Descriptive analysis of the field study sample

To apply the study tool After reviewing the questionnaire, the researcher resorted to distributing it to the intended study sample. The data was transcribed and entered into statistical software SPSS ,where nominal variables (strongly agree ,(agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree) were converted into quantitative variables (5, 4, 3, 2, 1), respectively

Analyze and discuss the results of the statements

:computerization of the tax system :Analysis and discussion of the first axis .Firstly

This axis aims to know the computerization of the tax system. To test this axis, it is necessary to indicate the direction of the opinions of the study sample members for each of its statements

Table No. (2)

Frequency distribution of the study sample members' answers to the first axis statement

D agree of approval	standard deviation	Arithme tic mean	I totally agree	I agree	neutral	I do not agree	Strongly Disagre e	The ferry
			Repetiti on	Repetit ion	Repetition	Repeti tion	Repetit ion	
			The ratio	The ratio	The ratio	The ratio	The ratio	
I agree	1.157	3.48	26 17.3%	68 45.3%	15 10.0%	34 22.7%	7 4.7%	The Bureau has an accurate information base about taxpayers
neu tral	1.265	3.31	24 16.0%	62 41.3%	17 11.3%	31 20.7%	16 10.7%	The Bureau works to update the taxpayer database periodically
I agree	1.016	4.03	49 32.7%	80 53.3%	3 2.0%	12 8.0%	6 4.0%	Every registered taxpayer has a tax identification number that is used for basic compliance duties

I totally agree	.973	4.21	68 45.3%	63 42.0%	7 4.7%	7 4.7%	5 3.3%	The computerized tax system helps speed up business completion
I agree	1.296	3.69	42 28.0%	68 45.3%	9 6.0%	13 8.7%	18 12.0%	The computerized tax system provides a secure online portal for registering and updating data
I agree	1.252	3.83	51 34.0%	64 42.7%	6 4.0%	16 10.7%	13 8.7%	The computerized tax system reduces the cost of inventory assessment and collection
I agree	1.152	3.95	50 33.3%	75 50.0%	4 2.7%	9 6.0%	12 8.0%	The Bureau is interested in implementing the electronic invoice system to achieve tax justice
neutral	1.094	4.07	59 39.3%	70 46.7%	3 2.0%	9 6.0%	9 6.0%	The electronic invoice application reduces the use of arbitrary estimates
neutral	1.362	3.21	25 16.7%	57 38.0%	17 11.3%	26 17.3%	25 16.7%	A modern communications network is available to serve the tax system used in the Bureau
neutral	1.452	3.11	24 16.0%	57 38.0%	17 11.3%	15 10.0%	37 24.7%	The Bureau deals with consulting companies that provide it with up-to-date information about technology in the tax field
I agree	.747	3.69	418 27.9%	664 44.3%	98 6.5%	172 11.5%	148 9.9%	Computerization of the tax system

Source: Researcher's preparations from field study data, 2023 AD

of the results of the first axis (**computerization of the tax system**). We find that he It is clear from Table No. (2) obtained an arithmetic mean of (3.69), that is, **agree** according to the five-point Likert scale. That is, the majority of .respondents strongly agree with what was stated in the first axis: computerization of the tax system

:evaluating internal control :Analyze and discuss the statements of the second axis .

. This topic aims to know **the evaluation of internal control** In order to test this axis, it is necessary to indicate the .direction of the opinions of the study sample members for each statement of this axis

Table No. (3)

Frequency distribution of the study sample members' answers to the second axis statements

Degree of approval	standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	I totally agree	I agree	neutral	I do not agree	Strongly Disagree	The ferry
			Repetition	Repetition	Repetition	Repetition	Repetition	
			The ratio	The ratio	The ratio	The ratio	The ratio	
I agree	1.313	3.43	27 18.0%	73 48.7%	9 6.0%	20 13.3%	21 14.0%	Procedures for evaluating internal control include whether internal control was carried out according to plan or not
I agree	.879	4.11	48 32.0%	85 56.7%	8 5.3%	4 2.7%	5 3.3%	Correcting errors and understanding why they occurred helps in understanding and evaluating internal control
neutral	1.436	3.33	31 20.7%	62 41.3%	15 10.0%	10 6.7%	32 21.3%	The Audit Department at the Bureau prepares a report on the effectiveness of internal control and submits it to senior management periodically
I agree	1.418	3.39	33 22.0%	61 40.7%	17 11.3%	9 6.0%	30 20.0%	The internal auditor submits a report to evaluate internal control by addressing deviations and weaknesses
I agree	1.391	3.18	22 14.7%	63 42.0%	16 10.7%	18 12.0%	31 20.7%	The Bureau's administration takes appropriate measures in response to audit reports on internal control
I agree	1.078	3.92	47 31.3%	71 47.3%	12 8.0%	13 8.7%	7 4.7%	The presence of an organizational structure with an appropriate division of functional

								responsibilities and a statement of the limits of powers helps in evaluating internal control
neutral	1.295	3.01	18 12.0%	48 32.0%	26 17.3%	34 22.7%	24 16.0%	The Bureau has an effective and appropriate system for communications and information exchange between all administrative levels
neutral	1.424	3.00	23 15.3%	48 32.0%	19 12.7%	26 17.3%	34 22.7%	The Bureau has a specialized and independent department for processing data electronically in the organizational structure
neutral	1.486	2.98	25 16.7%	48 32.0%	16 10.7%	21 14.0%	40 26.7%	A set of controls and supervisory procedures are used on programs and files to ensure the integrity of the internal control evaluation and detect errors if they occur
neutral	1.475	3.18	28 18.7%	58 38.7%	13 8.7%	15 10.0%	36 24.0%	The Bureau's electronic data is kept in external storage means to ensure its retrieval in the event of loss
neutral	.888	3.35	302 20.1%	617 41.1%	151 10.1%	170 11.3%	260 17.3%	Internal control evaluation

Source: Researcher’s preparations from field study data, 2023 AD

of the results of the second axis (**evaluating internal control**) that we find that it obtained It is clear from Table No. (3) an arithmetic mean of (3.5), meaning neutral. According to the five–point Likert scale. That is, the majority of respondents are neutral to what was stated in the terms of the second axis, evaluating internal control

: Secondly, analyze and discuss the results of the axes

Computerization of the tax system :of the first axis the results Analyze and discuss .1

This axis aims to know the computerization of the tax system . To test this axis, a single–sample t–test was used for the .answers of the study sample members

Table No. (7)

The mean and one-sample test for Computerization of the tax system answers

the decision	Relative importance	Moral	Degrees of freedom	T-Calculated	Phrase	M
Statistically significant	69.6%	.000	149	5.081	The Bureau has an accurate information base about taxpayers	1
Statistically significant	66.3%	.003	149	3.035	The Bureau works to update the taxpayer database periodically	2
Statistically significant	80.5%	.000	149	12.373	Every registered taxpayer has a tax identification number that is used for basic compliance duties	3
Statistically significant	84.3%	.000	149	15.267	The computerized tax system helps speed up business completion	4
Statistically significant	73.7%	.000	149	6.489	The computerized tax system provides a secure online portal for registering and updating data	5
Statistically significant	76.5%	.000	149	8.088	The computerized tax system reduces the cost of inventory, assessment and collection	6
Statistically significant	78.9%	.000	149	10.069	The Bureau is interested in implementing the electronic invoice system to achieve tax justice	7
Statistically significant	81.5%	.000	149	12.021	The electronic invoice application reduces the use of arbitrary estimates	8
Statistically significant	64.1%	.065	149	1.858	A modern communications network is available to serve the tax system used in the Bureau	9

Statistica lly significan t	62.1%	.370	149	.899	The Bureau deals with consulting companies that provide it with up-to-date information about technology in the tax field	10
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Source: Prepared by the researcher from 2023 field study data

:It is clear from Table No. (7) that

The value of the t-test calculated for the significance of the differences between members of the study sample who . 1 agreed, neutral, and disagreed with what was stated in the first statement was (5.081). The value of the significant study variables was also (0.00), which is less than the significance level (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149) and a significance level of 5. %, which indicates that there are statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample .members and in favor of those who agree that the Bureau should have an accurate information base about tax payers

,The value of the t-test calculated to indicate the differences between members of the study sample who agreed .2 and the value of the significant study ,(3.035) neutral, and disagreed with what was stated in the second statement was variables was (0.00), which is less than the level of significance (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149), which indicates There are statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of those who are .neutral. The Bureau works to update the database of taxpayers periodically

,The value of the t-test calculated to indicate the differences between the members of the study sample who agreed .3 neutral, and disagreed with what was stated in the third statement was (12.373), and the value of the study’s significant variables was (0.00), which is less than the level of significance (.05) at a degree of freedom (149). This indicates that there are statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of those who agree .that every registered taxpayer possesses a tax identification number that is used for basic compliance obligations

,The value of the t-test calculated to indicate the differences between the members of the study sample who agreed .4) neutral, and disagreed with what was stated in the fourth statement was 15.267 and the value of the study’s significant ,(variables was (0.000), which is less than the level of significance (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149), which indicates There are statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of those who .strongly agree that the computerized tax system helps in speeding up business completion

,The value of the t-test calculated to indicate the differences between members of the study sample who agreed .5) neutral, and disagreed with what was stated in the fifth statement was 6.489 and the value of the study’s significant ,(variables was (0.000), which is less than the level of significance (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149), which indicates There are statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of those who .agree that the computerized tax system provides a secure port via the Internet for registering and updating data

,The value of the t-test calculated to indicate the differences between members of the study sample who agree, neutral .6 and the value of the study’s significant variables ,(8.088) and disagree with what was stated in the sixth statement was was (0.000), which is less than the level of significance (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149), which indicates There are statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of those who agree that the .computerized tax system reduces the cost of inventory, assessment and collection

,The value of the t-test calculated to indicate the differences between members of the study sample who agreed .7) neutral, and disagreed with what was stated in the seventh statement was 10.069 and the value of the study’s ,(significant variables was (0.000), which is less than the level of significance (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149), which indicates There are statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of those .who agree that the Bureau should pay attention to implementing the electronic invoice system to achieve tax justice

.8 The value of the t-test calculated to indicate the differences between members of the study sample who agree, neutral () and disagree with what was stated in the eighth statement was 12.021 and the value of the significant variables of the study was (0.000), which is less than the level of significance (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149), which indicates There are statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of those who are neutral regarding the application of the electronic invoice, which reduces the use of arbitrary estimates

.9 The value of the t-test calculated to indicate the differences between members of the study sample who agree, neutral and the value of the study's significant variables (1.858) and disagree with what was stated in the ninth statement was (0.000), which is less than the level of significance (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149), which indicates There are statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of the neutrals regarding the availability of a modern communications network to serve the tax system used in the office

.10 The value of the t-test calculated to indicate the differences between members of the study sample who agree and the value of the significant study (899.) neutral, and disagree with what was stated in the tenth statement was variables was (0.370), which is greater than the significance level of (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149). This indicates that there are no statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of those who are neutral about the Bureau dealing with consulting companies that provide it with modern information about technology in the tax field

the T It is clear to the researcher from Table (3/3/12) that all probability values (statistical significance) corresponding to are less than the level of significance (0.05). This means that value calculated for the significance of the differences there are statistically significant differences between the answers of the two respondents, that is, there is statistical significance in the distribution of responses. The sample members asked the different answer options (strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree), meaning that the answers of the sample members are biased toward one option over another. In general, we conclude that most of the sample members strongly agree with the axis statements From all of the above results regarding the first axis of the study, it indicates that the hypothesis has been verified, which states: **There are statistically significant differences regarding... Computerization of the tax system**

evaluating internal control :the second axis the results of analyze and discuss ,Secondly

This axis aims to know **the evaluation of internal control**, and to test this axis , it is necessary to indicate the direction of the opinions of the members of the study sample for each statement of this axis. The one-sample test was used for the answers of the study sample members to the axis of evaluating internal control

Table No. (8)

Arithmetic mean and one- sample test the internal control The answers of the study sample members to evaluation axis

the decision	Relative importance	Moral	Degrees of freedom	T - Calculated	Phrase	M
Statistically significant	68.7%	.000	149	4.042	Procedures for evaluating internal control include whether internal control was carried out according to plan or not	1

Statistically significant	82.3%	.000	149	15.516	Correcting errors and understanding why they occurred helps in understanding and evaluating internal control	2
Statistically significant	66.7%	.005	149	2.843	The Audit Department at the Bureau prepares a report on the effectiveness of internal control and submits it to senior management periodically	3
Statistically significant	67.7%	.001	149	3.340	The internal auditor submits a report to evaluate internal control by addressing deviations and weaknesses	4
Statistically significant	63.6%	.115	149	1.585	The Bureau's administration takes appropriate measures in response to audit reports on internal control	5
Statistically significant	78.4%	.000	149	10.456	The presence of an organizational structure with an appropriate division of functional responsibilities and a statement of the limits of powers helps in evaluating internal control	6
Statistically significant	60.3%	.900	149	.126	The Bureau has an effective and appropriate system for communications and information exchange between all administrative levels	7
Statistically significant	60.0%	1.000	149	.000	The Bureau has a specialized and independent department for processing data electronically in the organizational structure	8
Statistically significant	59.6%	.869	149	-.165	A set of controls and supervisory procedures are used on programs and files to ensure the integrity of the internal control .evaluation and detect errors if they occur	9
Statistically significant	63.6%	.137	149	1.495	The Bureau's electronic data is kept in external storage means to ensure its retrieval in the event of loss	10

Source: Prepared by the researcher from 2023 field study data

The value of the t-test calculated for the significance of the differences between members of the study sample who agreed, neutral, and disagreed with what was stated in the first statement was (4.042), and the value of the significant study variables was (0.00), which is less than the significance level of (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149) and a significance level of 5. %, which indicates that there are statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of those who agree that internal control evaluation procedures include whether internal control was carried out according to what was planned or not

.2 The value of the t-test calculated to indicate the differences between members of the study sample who agreed and the value of the significant study variables was (0.00), which is less than the level of significance (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149), which indicates There are statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of those who agree to correct cases of errors and understanding why they occurred helps in understanding and evaluating internal control.

.3 The value of the t-test calculated to indicate the differences between members of the study sample who agree, neutral and disagree with what was stated in the third statement was (2.843), and the value of the significant variables of the study was (0.00), which is less than the level of significance (.05) at a degree of freedom (149). Which indicates that there are statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of the neutrals. The Audit Department at the Bureau prepares a report on the effectiveness of internal control and submits it to senior management periodically.

.4 The value of the t-test calculated to indicate the differences between members of the study sample who agreed and the value of the study's significant variables was (0.000), which is less than the level of significance (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149), which indicates There are statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of those who agree to the internal auditor submitting a report to evaluate internal control by addressing deviations and weaknesses.

.5 The value of the t-test calculated to indicate the differences between members of the study sample who agree, neutral and disagree with what was stated in the fifth statement was (0.000), which is less than the level of significance (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149), which indicates There are statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of those who agree that the Bureau's administration takes appropriate measures in response to audit reports on internal control.

.6 The value of the t-test calculated to indicate the differences between members of the study sample who agreed and the value of the study's significant variables was (0.000), which is less than the level of significance (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149), which indicates There are statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of those who agree to the existence of an organizational structure with an appropriate division of functional responsibilities and a statement of the limits of powers that helps in evaluating internal control.

.7 The value of the t-test calculated to indicate the differences between members of the study sample who agree, neutral and disagree with what was stated in the seventh statement was .126 and the value of the significant study variables was (0.000), which is less than the level of significance (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149). This indicates that there are statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of neutrals, provided that the office has an effective and appropriate system for communications and information exchange between all administrative levels.

.8 The value of the t-test calculated for the significance of the differences between members of the study sample who agree, neutral, and disagree with what was stated in the eighth statement was significant variables was (1.000), which is greater than the significance level (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149). This indicates that there are no statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of the neutrals regarding the fact that the Bureau has a specialized and independent department for processing data electronically in the organizational structure.

.9 The value of the t-test calculated for the significance of the differences between members of the study sample who agreed, neutral, and disagreed with what was stated in the ninth statement was The value of the study's (.165-) agreed, neutral, and disagreed with what was stated in the ninth statement was

.variables was also significant (0.869), which is greater than the significance level (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149) Which indicates that there are no statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of the neutrals regarding the use of a set of controls and supervisory procedures on programs and files to ensure .the safety of electronic operation and to detect errors if they occur

,The value of the t-test calculated to indicate the differences between members of the study sample who agree .10 and the significant value of the study ,(1.495) neutral, and disagree with what was stated in the tenth statement was variables was (.137), which is greater than the significance level (0.05) at a degree of freedom (149). This indicates that there are no statistically significant differences between the answers of the sample members and in favor of the neutrals provided that the electronic data of the office is kept in external storage means to ensure its retrieval in the event of its , .loss

the T It is clear to the researcher from Table (4/3/13) that all probability values (statistical significance) corresponding to are less than the level of significance (0.05). This means that value calculated for the significance of the differences there are statistically significant differences between the answers of the two respondents, that is, there is statistical ,significance in the distribution of responses. The sample members asked the different answer options (strongly agree agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree), meaning that the sample members' answers are biased toward one option second axis On the phrases of the .are neutral over another. In general, we conclude that most of the sample members .

,From all of the above results regarding the second axis of the study, it indicates that the hypothesis has been verified .Internal control evaluation ...which states: **There are statistically significant differences regarding**

:Second: Analyze and discuss the results of the hypotheses

:Correlation coefficient -1

The aim of calculating the correlation coefficient is to measure the relationship between the axes that make up the .variables of the study

Table (12)
Calculate correlation coefficients

Internal control evaluation	Computerization of the tax system	Interviewer	
.685**	1	Pearson correlation	Computerization of the tax system
.000		Moral value	
150	150	Sample volume	
1	.685**	Pearson correlation	Internal control evaluation
	.000	Moral value	
150	150	Sample volume	

:Source **Prepared by the researcher from 2023 field study data**

after Study and calculate the correlation coefficients in the table the previous We notice that There is a relationship Between direct And self indication Statistic High **evaluating internal control and**) Between (**computerizing the tax system**) and

through the value of the morale level, which is equal to (0.000), which is less than the (**activating tax governance** :**Simple regression analysis** –customary value (0.05). 2

It is considered a measure of the quality of the relationship between two variables, and in many studies the relationship between more than two variables is a relationship of dependence (regression). Simple linear regression is considered a .statistical method that is used to measure the relationship between two variables in the form of a function relationship One of the variables is called an independent variable and it is the one that causes the change. The dependent variable .and the other is a dependent variable, and this relationship is represented by the straight line equation

:(**evaluation of internal control and computerization of the tax system**) **Regression analysis between variables** .1

Table No. (13)

Results of simple linear regression analysis to measure the relationship between the tax system computerization variable and internal control evaluation

Interpretation	Probability value(Sig (	) test (	Regressi on coefficients	
Not significant	.194	1.305	.three hundred fifty	$\hat{B}_0$
Moral	.000	11.440	.815	$\hat{B}_1$
			.685a	Correlation) coefficient (R
			.469	The coefficient of determination (R²)
The model is significant			130.875	F) to choose (
$\hat{y} = (0.350) + .815X$				

Source: Prepared by the researcher from the field study, 2023 AD

:(13) .It is clear from Table No

1. The estimation results showed that there is a strong direct correlation between **the computerization of the tax system** as an independent variable and **the evaluation of internal control** as a dependent variable, through the .value of the simple correlation coefficient that reached (0.685)
2. was (0.469). This value indicates that **computerization of the tax (R²)** The value of the coefficient of determination .**system** as an independent variable contributes (47%) to **the evaluation of internal control** (the dependent variable)
3. After using the analysis of variance test, it was found that the simple linear regression model was significant, as the value of theF test reached (.which is an indication of the significance level (0.000) ,(130.875
4. We find that the constant of the regression model is equal to (0.350), which is the value of **the internal control ,evaluation** when **the computerization of the tax system** is equal to zero (lack of computerization of the tax system) while we find the value of the parameter of computerization of the tax system equal to (0.815) and its accompanying value equals (0.000), which is less than the customary value. (0.05) This means that there is a statistically significant . relationship between **the computerization of the tax system** and **the evaluation of internal control**

From the above, we conclude that the hypothesis of the first study, which states: “ **There is a relationship between the computerization of the tax system and the evaluation of internal control has been achieved** .

: First: discussion Results

:The study reached the following results

- 1- The available information base is not updated on a continuous basis, and thus taxpayer information becomes outdated .
- 2- The computerized system helps speed up the completion of work if modern communication networks and good infrastructure are available.
- 3- The Internal Audit Department at the Bureau submits a report on internal control and indicates the strengths and weaknesses.
- 4- that Computerization the system Tax help in activation Governance .tax
- 5- The presence of an organizational structure with an appropriate division of functional responsibilities and a statement .of the limits of powers helps in evaluating internal control
- 6- The salaries and allowances of the Bureau’s employees are not commensurate with the nature of the work and the effort expended

:Second: Recommendations

- 1- .Increase the state’s interest in the computing project, provide the required financial support for it, and make it a priority
- 2- .Expanding the use of electronic invoices and prohibiting work without identification numbers
- 3- .Paying attention to the internal control report and working to address deviations
- 4- Updating control procedures periodically and paying attention to procedures for monitoring the system and procedures .for security and confidentiality of customer data
- 5- the job on to improve Structure Infrastructure To benefit from Technologies .existing
- 6- more Advertisements And intensify Campaigns For my payers Tax on Services e In the office And benefits Use it .
- 7- ,Publish a report on the Bureau’s website about the contribution of taxes to the state budget, with numbers and data and place it in the portal of all taxpayer services offices.

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